

By

This is a collection of ideas, stories, pictures and photographs belonging to all of the children from **XXXX, i** in Carlow, who took part in a research project called, 'Can we see our voices'? The adult researcher Muireann Ranta and her assistant Hazel the Hedgehog supported the children under their participatory rights of the Conventions on the Rights of the Children (UNCRC) to be involved in research about how young children learn in, through, about and for Nature.

Every child living in Ireland has a right to learn about Nature. It is called **Article 29 1 (e)** and is outlined as follows,

1. States Parties agree that the education of the child shall be directed to:

(e) The development of respect for the natural environment.

(UNCRC, 1989).

We would like to invite you to take the time to hear these ideas, to be inspired by the activities that were developed by the children themselves and to use the resources in the project to further support more children to enjoy their education rights in Nature.

Thank-you.

Can we see our voices ?

How to draw spiders

This is a spider with no body.

You can draw circles.

SPIDERS

Spiders eat meat. Meat can be ham or chicken. They have 8 hairy legs and 48 knees. They are insects. Some insects live in leaves and some insects live indoors.

There is a spider living in my Nanny's house. This isn't any spider. This spider lives in picture frames.

In the kitchen in my house and my Nana walked in and she screamed like this ...AHHH... and she got her shoe and guess what she did She did this (bangs table) to the spider... My dad always puts them outside when they are gigantic spiders like this !

Spiders make webs and use webs to catch flies and they live in the webs. I know spiders have 8 legs but I gave mine 10. This is pink and has red and the rest is blue. This is a tarantula.

The spider is gold and the rest is gold and the inside of the big gold is pink. I found a baby one in my house. It was in my bedroom and I wanted to bring it downstairs but Mammy was scared. It was funny.

How to draw hedgehogs

Like a circle but squiggly for the spikes

I was on my holidays and I was in this cave, and there was spikey things hanging from the roof and I was thinking to myself a hedgehog must be living in this cave 'cos of the spikes.

Worms eat dirt , old leaves and old food.

Worms are not boys or girls or spiders. They are good for the garden, their poo helps things grow. They have no legs. I like putting him on my hand.

Ants talk to one another with their feelers.

The queen is the Mammy and the dad is the Daddy. The ants eat old food.

Bees. One time I saw a bee in the real world and I saw it and I cuddled it. It was real and alive . It was like a little pet and it didn't even sting me. I have a beehive and my bees are lovely and if somebody sat on them, they wouldn't sting . The bees are making honey for everybody.

Woodlouse goes into a ball like a hedgehog. One time we went to my uncles, and there was a ton of them there., and we found a lot, we found a baby one, a big one, a Daddy and a Mammy.

Ladybirds are always in the Summer. Everyday I go out to my Gran Gran's houseshe has a lady-bird house and every time I put my hand like this and it crawls on my hand and then I feed him ...

Earwigs. I call them pinchers.

Slugs and **S**nails' bodies are called a foot. If you lie on the ground and go in and out you can move like a slug. It's fun.

They are in the little
holes ... in the nest
... cos they are
asleep and when
they wake up It's
Spring and you can
see them again and
then you look at
them with your
magnifying glasses ..

Someone else told the same
Hibernating and hibernating...
So bears do and cub bears and
squirrels do and snails do.
Because every different animal
not hibernates and hibernates.

I want to see a slug

I don't want to touch
it or my hands will get
slimey

Look the wiggly worm...
...look the wiggly worm

Oh it feels sluggy

Soft!

so cute

We haven't seen any ants

He is under the leaf where you
are doing it

Roby the Rob

Hazel

Lily Lily Lil

Goldfinch not fish

Blue Tit

Longtailed Tit

Sparrow

What you need to make a birdfeeder

Apples

I am cleaning the apple but I am not finished yet with cleaning .

I like them peeled.

I eat them with the peel.

I eat them without the peel.

I want it like a big one and you give it to me.... Like the one with the skin on it

You can't eat all the apples... you will get sea sick

No.. You have to eat one apple a day.

You will need a bowl.... I just want to eat it with my hands

Peanut Butter

I want to smell it smells like peanut butter

No don't be touching it with your fingers I need a knife

(***if you don't like the stickiness you can tie a string to the apple and use a knife.)

Where do you paint the peanut butter ?

So put it around the little.... Over the lines And then around

And when you paint the peanut butter on the apple, you get bird seeds.

I don't like it.

I hate peanut butter.It's yucky for your throat It's not good for your mouth

I just tasted it I like doing stuff with it .. But I just hate, I just hate eating it

Birdseed

Let's take the seeds outside Yeah if it's inside and then the birds will fly and we will have to wait a long long time

Then you put some sprinkles on it..... They are little seeds

You rolled it around

Round and round

Cos we don't want to waste the seeds...

Look at mine.....It's so sprinkly.... It's all sprinkles... Can I bring it home ?

I want to hang it In the tree.... No I want to hang it on the Christmas tree.....with the string.

Do you know there are big birds and little birds and Mama birds and they fly and grab snails so that they can eat them That's sad like...because like they will get dead...the snails.

The birdy eat it The robin didn't come to eat it but the bird did and I whispered very quiet

Trees

We planted the trees

I planted a tree before

I planted a treeI think they are growing

They are growing to the same size as the other trees

It's so fun to mess around..

I liked the digging

I liked when I was measuring my height myself

Flowers

Soil

We planted in it

They grew.....They grew alot

Can I have a magnifying glass ?

A hole ..and a little hole...and I found a big hole

Look what's going on the ground.....grass

Me got a hole

I found a little leaf... a stone

These stones might grow ... and rasp-berries as well

Look look...look at the nut

Oh it looks bigger

Look Look your baby plants are growing...

That was a weed...no no..it's a wiggly
worm

But why can't we dig up here ?

Only ever step on these

But I'm not going to dig up these ones

Is it a crocus ?

It's going to be yellow

It looks like they are growing out
noodles...like grass

Will I keep the stone to take away ?

SAND

I love it so much cos I can do
what I want

I want to show you something
... you put the sand in there ...
and it turns
around....Watch..watch !

But I'm not going to dig up
these ones, I'm going to go dig
up in that sandpit

I play with the sand

I liked the digging

I was just lying here

Littering

I know what to call these two frogs ...Ben and Ben.... No Feet Frog No Ben and Holly... no Jumpoo...

They live in the pond.

But why are they so mad ?

Cos they don't like the water..

Why did they have a fight ?

Maybe he had a bad dream or something

James H. Reece

ASH
CH

It looks like the blue sky.... The sky doesn't look blue now (points outside)

A ladybird...it looks like it's just sitting there

Lovely

I think it looks kinda real cos it's got loads of bugs

But where is his friend now ?

Why was it smelly ? Ugghhhh!

Slime ! Oh yuck !

Why did he go to a stinky one ?

It looks blaghhhh!!!

Trash...Trashy

But why is it so dirty ? But why is there chocolate ?

Litteringthat's a broken tyre.

Waste Management

We could do this with our fingers when the rubbish comes ...you never put your hands in bins cos they are very dirty and very bad

Do you know the way someone can not get sore fingers ever..... you put a .. and punch down on it....I have one of them.... I have a pedalling bin that you push for nappies.

1

A banana skin and an orange skin goes into this bin. ... Wait is it a compost bin ? A banana peel bin

I have some orange skin and I'm going to put it in here ...because it has a picture on it

2.

That's my raisin pack.
Card....cardboard..
in the blue bin.

Yesterday my ma put something
dirty and I said make sure it's
clean first !!!!

I wash mine.

There's nothing on it.

3.

I'm after picking up a bit of rubbish and put it in the binwhere is that one going to go ?

The cheese wrap goes into the rubbish bin

**Yoghurt suckers.... Yoghurt rubbish ...
in the rubbish bin.**

**The cling film goes to the rubbish
bin.**

**Mammy see that one, it goes on this
one and then it goes**

What can go in your Recycling Bin...

A list....on the wall

I want this one ... can I bring this one home ? ..Well I want to bring this one home

Are we going to keep these magnets ? It's moving, it was moving...it's moving

It's like a cookie

Purple.....I picked blue....red....green

I have a blue paper, a blue magnet and a blue scissors

I need to cut it....I need to cut itcut this....you may cut it...

I need glue

I will help her.....I can help you

But I am going to put the glue on it.....

I know how, I know how I'm going to do it

Can I make another list ?

What can go in your Recycling Bin...

PAPER

Newspapers
Magazines
Junk mail
Envelopes
Paper
Phone books
Catalogues
Tissue boxes
Sugar bags
Calendars

Dairies
Letters
Computer paper
Used beverage
Juice cartons
Milk cartons
Egg boxes
Holiday brochures
Paper potato bags

CARDBOARD

Food boxes
Packaging boxes
Cereal boxes
Kitchen towel tubes

ALUMINIUM & STEEL CANS

Drink cans
Steel cans
Pet food cans
Food cans
Biscuit tins
Soup tins

TIN

Always make sure all materials are clean dry and loose before putting them in the recycling bin

PLASTIC PACKAGING (PP)

Yogurt containers
Margarine tubs
Rigid food packaging
Liquid soap containers
Fruit containers

PLASTIC BOTTLES (PET 1)

Mineral bottles
Water bottles
Mouthwash bottles
Salad dressing bottles

PLASTIC BOTTLES (HDPE2)

Milk bottles
Juice bottles
Cosmetic bottles
Shampoo bottles
Household cleaning bottles
Laundry detergent bottles
Window cleaning bottles
Bathroom bottles

